

Kinetics of potassium adsorption and desorption in some soils of West Bengal

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Abstract : Kinetics of potassium (K) adsorption and desorption were studied in eight soils of widely varying physico-chemical properties with a view to identifying the major rate-limiting steps. The study was described by using first-order, Elovich, parabolic-diffusion, power function and zero-order equations. From the overall studies of kinetic equations, it was found that the parabolic-diffusion equation as well as the first-order equation was equally good to describe the adsorption and desorption of K in soils which suggests that the given adsorption and desorption processes tended to be diffusion controlled. The rate constants were closely related to the clay mineralogical make-up of the given soils. In general, the soils dominated by kaolinite, exhibited lower adsorption rate coefficient (k_a) than the other soils studied, while showing much higher desorption rate coefficient (k_d). This was attributed to the absence of specific sites for K in the clay fraction of these soils. From the Gibbs standard free energy change (ΔG°) values, the Gayeshpur, Memari, Goaltore and Kalimpong soils were found to favour Ca-K exchange.

Keywords : Kinetics, potassium, adsorption, desorption, first-order, Elovich, parabolic-diffusion, power function, zero-order.

Introduction

Several models and techniques have been employed successfully over the years in the study of K kinetic reactions on pure clays and soils¹⁻¹⁰ to identify the major rate-limiting steps in K adsorption and release in soil. Both the miscible displacement and the batch techniques are popular and have been used with great success. Both the techniques are also known to yield similar results when similar time intervals are used¹¹. The efforts to describe K release kinetics have led to use several models which include parabolic diffusion, first-order rate, Elovich equation, power function equation and the zero-order equation¹²⁻¹⁴. The kinetics of K adsorption and desorption in multireactive heterogeneous soil systems have successfully employed the first-order and the parabolic diffusion laws⁷. Potassium release from calcareous soils using a Ca-saturated resin did not conform to the first order kinetics¹³ but the same from non-exchangeable pool to H-resin conformed to the first-order kinetics⁹. However, several workers^{10,15} revealed that K release from micaeous minerals as well as from most soil fractions were diffusion controlled and the kinetics of exchange conformed to the parabolic diffusion law.

It is recognized that soils contain sites of differing reactivity for K ions^{16,17}. Jardine and Sparks⁷ observed the rapid kinetics of exchange to external planner sites, slow kinetics of exchange to inter-lattice exchange sites, and intermediate kinetics of exchange to inter-lattice-edge sites. Application of parabolic law is based on the assumption that the adsorption process could not be fully explained by either 'film diffusion' or 'intraparticle diffusion' theory⁷. The objective of the present study is to evaluate the kinetics of potassium exchange in soil by following the batch technique with a discussion on the usefulness of rate-laws in soil systems.

Results and discussion

The important physicochemical properties of the soil samples collected from eight locations of West Bengal are presented in Table 1. Adsorption and desorption processes of ions in soils control the availability of nutrients and the soil properties largely influence the processes. The results of statistical analysis obtained by plots, which were fits between the models and the experimental data, are reflected by the R^2 and S.E. of the estimates. The various kinetic equations along with assessment of the

Table 1. Physicochemical characteristics of the soils

Soil characteristics	Location of soils							
	Gayeshpur	Memari	Jhargram	Goaltore	Kakdwip	Canning	Kalimpong	Islampur
Taxonomic classification	Fine loamy Aeric Fluvaquent	Fine Aeric Haplaquept	Coarse loamy typic Haplustalfs	Coarse loamy typic Haplustalfs	Typic Haplaquepts	Coarse loamy Typic Ustifluvents	Loamy skeletal Lithic Udorthents	Coarse loamy Typic Fluvaquents
pH (1 : 2.5 w/v) (soil : water)	5.98	6.35	5.22	4.80	5.34	4.35	5.44	5.61
E.C. (d Sm ⁻¹) (1 : 2.5 :: soil : water)	0.13	0.10	0.04	0.08	3.49	2.26	0.04	0.04
CEC (cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹)	24.3	22.1	9.20	10.1	20.5	19.3	12.0	13.5
Water holding capacity (%)	28.3	23.6	8.10	8.00	49.2	51.7	48.6	46.5
Clay content (%)	44.3	41.8	25.2	29.4	55.6	53.5	13.8	12.2
Organic carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	6.11	7.10	3.53	4.11	10.4	9.62	15.6	11.0
Exchangeable (Ca ²⁺ + Mg ²⁺) (cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹)	6.11	7.02	2.61	2.54	7.95	6.12	1.99	2.36
Exchangeable Na ⁺ (cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹)	0.43	0.62	0.27	0.32	3.21	2.68	0.25	0.33
Exchangeable K ⁺ (cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹)	0.20	0.40	0.21	0.08	0.91	0.87	0.13	0.31
Texture	Sandy clay loam	Sandy clay loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Clay loam	Clay loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam

Table 2. Semi-quantitative (percent) composition of clay minerals in clay fraction of soils

Location of soils	Smectite	Chlorite	Inter-stratified	Illite	Kaolinite	Feldspars	Quartz
Gayeshpur	8	27	5	45	10	3	2
Memari	19	-	4	54	19	3	1
Jhargram	4	-	-	31	61	2	2
Goaltore	10	-	11	24	49	4	2
Kakdwip	14	16	8	42	14	4	2
Canning	14	14	6	42	17	5	2
Kalimpong	10	16	18	35	16	3	2
Islampur	12	8	16	38	18	5	3

best-fit equation were presented in Tables 3 to 6. The overall studies of kinetic equations reveal that the parabolic-diffusion equation and the first-order equation were equally good to describe the adsorption and desorption of K in soils.

Results of statistical analysis showed that the parabolic-diffusion equation described the kinetics of K adsorption and desorption best in six out of the given eight soils, as characterized by the highest coefficient of determination (R^2) value and the lowest standard error (S.E.)

of estimate value. This finding is in good agreement with the results obtained by Chute and Quirk¹⁵, Evans and Jurinak²⁵, Sparks *et al.*^{5,6}, Sparks and Jardine^{22,26}. The first-order was almost as good in describing the adsorption and desorption as evident from the corresponding high R^2 and low values of S.E. (Tables 3–6). This observation contrasts with that of Martin and Sparks¹⁴ but in agreement with several others^{5,6,22,23,26,27}. This suggests that the given adsorption and desorption processes tended to be diffusion controlled. A straight linear relationship

Fig. 1. First-order plots of potassium adsorption and desorption on soils.

obtained (Figs. 1 to 2) suggested that the intraparticle diffusion could be the rate-limiting process⁷. The Elovich equation similar to power function and zero-order equations did not adequately describe K adsorption and desorption of the samples employed in the study. The low R^2 values and relatively high values of S.E. of estimates of these equations provide a strong case for its non-fit.

The K adsorption rate coefficients (k_a) in the Memari and Gayeshpur soils (Table 7) were high among the soils studied, being in the order of 4.2×10^{-5} and $3.45 \times 10^{-5} \text{ min}^{-1}$. This may possibly be related to the dominance (in its clay fraction) of micaceous minerals, smectite and illite which possessed a larger proportion of interlayer sites

besides the specific K fixation sites. Goulding²⁸ found strong K retention in the soils that contained substantial quantities of (2 : 1) clay minerals (as in these soils). Such minerals are readily accessible to K exchange in these soils, causing only film diffusion-controlled exchange. The soil of Jhargram exhibited a low k_a value ($1.92 \times 10^{-5} \text{ min}^{-1}$). The Jhargram soil is kaolinite dominated possessing very few exchange and K specific sites which may explain the corresponding low k_a value. The soils of Kakdwip and Canning exhibited a medium range of k_a values despite of containing high amount of clay and a good amount K bearing illite and smectite minerals in these soils. A high amount of soluble salts in these soils,

Fig. 2. Parabolic-diffusion plots of potassium adsorption and desorption on soils.

Table 3. Standard error of estimate (S.E.) and coefficient of determination (R^2) of various kinetic equations for K adsorption in the soils

Location of soils	First-order equation		Elovich equation		Parabolic-diffusion equation		Power-function equation		Zero-order equation	
	S.E.	R^2	S.E.	R^2	S.E.	R^2	S.E.	R^2	S.E.	R^2
Gayeshpur	0.0046	0.989 ^a	0.7790	0.854	0.0128	0.964	0.0245	0.873	0.2389	0.986
Memari	0.0098	0.964 ^a	0.6453	0.891	0.0117	0.958	0.0182	0.903	0.4451	0.948
Jhargram	0.0087	0.885	0.4553	0.902	0.0137	0.938 ^a	0.0174	0.907	0.5139	0.875
Goaltore	0.0107	0.929	0.3333	0.960	0.0056	0.987 ^a	0.0097	0.965	0.4899	0.914
Kakdwip	0.0054	0.975	0.5091	0.910	0.0080	0.981 ^a	0.0165	0.924	0.3132	0.966
Canning	0.0056	0.971	0.6007	0.898	0.0110	0.977 ^a	0.0224	0.912	0.3650	0.962
Kalimpong	0.0056	0.972	0.6123	0.934	0.0057	0.998 ^a	0.0267	0.954	0.4661	0.962
Islampur	0.0067	0.948	0.8453	0.883	0.0376	0.958 ^a	0.0526	0.917	0.5898	0.943

S.E. = mg per 100 g of soil.

^ais the best fit equation.

especially the Na-salts, is probably the reason for such low k_a values, when compared with that of the Memari and Gayeshpur soils. This gets a support from the high E.C. values and high exchangeable Na^+ contents in the former soils (Table 1). On the other hand, being illite and smectite dominated a very low content of clay in the soils

of Kalimpong and Islampur could possibly be the related with the corresponding low k_a values in these soils.

The kinetics of K desorption are known to be related to the clay mineralogy of soils²⁰. The soils from Jhargram and Goaltore are dominated by kaolinite and they exhibited rapid rates of K desorption. This is in agreement

Table 4. Various kinetic equations for K adsorption in the soils

Location of soils	First-order equation, $\log K =$	Elovich equation, $K_t =$	Parabolic-diffusion equation, $K_t/K_0 =$	Power-function equation, $\ln K_t =$	Zero-order equation, $K_0 - K_t =$
Gayeshpur	$1.362 - 0.0009 t$	$24.294 + 1.4182 \ln t$	$0.8482 + 0.0185 \sqrt{t}$	$3.2048 + 0.0485 \ln t$	$3.1331 - 0.0429 t$
Memari	$1.276 - 0.0011 t$	$28.404 + 1.388 \ln t$	$0.8691 + 0.0156 \sqrt{t}$	$3.3564 + 0.0420 \ln t$	$3.0659 - 0.0403 t$
Jhargram	$1.413 - 0.0005 t$	$21.984 + 1.0408 \ln t$	$0.8745 + 0.0150 \sqrt{t}$	$3.0993 + 0.0409 \ln t$	$2.2238 - 0.0289 t$
Goaltore	$1.293 - 0.0008 t$	$27.827 + 1.2315 \ln t$	$0.8818 + 0.0141 \sqrt{t}$	$3.3339 + 0.0386 \ln t$	$2.6204 - 0.0338 t$
Kakdwip	$1.371 - 0.0007 t$	$24.080 + 1.2208 \ln t$	$0.8656 + 0.0161 \sqrt{t}$	$3.1921 + 0.0433 \ln t$	$2.6735 - 0.0354 t$
Canning	$1.434 - 0.0007 t$	$20.176 + 1.3409 \ln t$	$0.8329 + 0.0201 \sqrt{t}$	$3.0219 + 0.0542 \ln t$	$2.9275 - 0.0391 t$
Kalimpong	$1.523 - 0.0007 t$	$13.172 + 1.7391 \ln t$	$0.7286 + 0.0326 \sqrt{t}$	$2.6316 + 0.0918 \ln t$	$3.7550 - 0.0497 t$
Islampur	$1.592 - 0.0006 t$	$7.4171 + 1.7465 \ln t$	$0.6784 + 0.0502 \sqrt{t}$	$2.1322 + 0.1319 \ln t$	$2.5332 - 0.0508 t$

$K = \text{mg L}^{-1}$ of K in solution,

$K_t = \text{mg}$ of K adsorbed per 100 g of soil at time t and

$K_0 = \text{mg}$ of K on the exchange sites of 100 g soil at equilibrium.

Table 5. Standard error of estimate (S.E.) and coefficient of determination (R^2) of various kinetic equations for K desorption in the soils

Location of soils	First-order equation		Elovich equation		Parabolic-diffusion equation		Power-function equation		Zero-order equation	
	S.E.	R^2	S.E.	R^2	S.E.	R^2	S.E.	R^2	S.E.	R^2
Gayeshpur	0.0029	0.891	0.8700	0.864	0.0314	0.965	0.0542	0.911	0.3108	0.983 ^a
Memari	0.0020	0.979 ^a	0.8864	0.898	0.0494	0.971	0.0779	0.953	0.5308	0.963
Jhargram	0.0034	0.975 ^a	0.5621	0.918	0.0198	0.975 ^a	0.0342	0.935	0.5042	0.934
Goaltore	0.0058	0.923	0.5010	0.961	0.0176	0.989 ^a	0.0271	0.979	0.7295	0.918
Kakdwip	0.0064	0.988 ^a	1.1168	0.913	0.0288	0.988 ^a	0.0552	0.969	0.6247	0.973
Canning	0.0118	0.967	1.1290	0.902	0.0354	0.978 ^a	0.0663	0.944	0.7433	0.958
Kalimpong	0.0114	0.665	0.6597	0.947	0.0232	0.995 ^a	0.0355	0.993	0.6153	0.953
Islampur	0.0181	0.730	0.8021	0.924	0.0491	0.976 ^a	0.0653	0.974	0.7369	0.935

S.E. = mg per 100 g of soil.

^ais the best fit equation.

Table 6. Various kinetic equations for K desorption in the soils

Location of soils	First-order equation, $\log (K_0 - K_t) =$	Elovich equation, $K_t =$	Parabolic-diffusion equation, $K_t/K_0 =$	Power-function equation, $\ln K_t =$	Zero-order equation, $K_0 - K_t =$
Gayeshpur	$1.226 - 0.0002 t$	$7.0198 + 1.6487 \ln t$	$0.6169 + 0.0465 \sqrt{t}$	$2.0801 + 0.1307 \ln t$	$3.6462 - 0.0495 t$
Memari	$1.416 - 0.0003 t$	$1.1774 + 1.9772 \ln t$	$0.3295 + 0.0803 \sqrt{t}$	$1.1259 + 0.2644 \ln t$	$4.3567 - 0.0576 t$
Jhargram	$1.059 - 0.0005 t$	$9.8136 + 1.4153 \ln t$	$0.7130 + 0.0344 \sqrt{t}$	$2.3447 + 0.0977 \ln t$	$3.0578 - 0.0402 t$
Goaltore	$1.280 - 0.0004 t$	$7.4183 + 1.8770 \ln t$	$0.6117 + 0.0461 \sqrt{t}$	$2.1388 + 0.1395 \ln t$	$4.0054 - 0.0516 t$
Kakdwip	$1.260 - 0.0012 t$	$2.9797 + 2.7200 \ln t$	$0.3936 + 0.0729 \sqrt{t}$	$1.6878 + 0.2306 \ln t$	$5.9408 - 0.0790 t$
Canning	$1.133 - 0.0014 t$	$4.1718 + 2.5826 \ln t$	$0.4478 + 0.0666 \sqrt{t}$	$1.8391 + 0.2048 \ln t$	$5.6172 - 0.0749 t$
Kalimpong	$1.087 - 0.0003 t$	$0.1835 + 2.0897 \ln t$	$0.2603 + 0.0880 \sqrt{t}$	$0.8781 + 0.3105 \ln t$	$4.5208 - 0.0589 t$
Islampur	$0.799 - 0.0006 t$	$0.3332 + 2.0973 \ln t$	$0.2691 + 0.0874 \sqrt{t}$	$0.931 + 0.3018 \ln t$	$4.5321 - 0.0594 t$

$K_0 = \text{total amount of K in mg that could be released and}$

$K_t = \text{mg of K adsorbed per 100 g of soil at time } t.$

Table 7. Kinetics of ionic reactions in soils by using batch technique

Location of soils	Adsorption rate coefficient (k_a) $\times 10^5$ (min^{-1})	Desorption rate coefficient (k_d) $\times 10^5$ (min^{-1})	Thermodynamic equilibrium constant for K adsorption ($K_{\text{eq}} = k_a/k_d$)	Standard free energy change of K adsorption (ΔG°) (kJ mol^{-1})
Gayeshpur	3.45	0.77	4.48	-3.74
Memari	4.22	1.15	3.66	-3.23
Jhargram	1.92	1.92	1.00	0
Goaltore	3.07	1.54	1.99	-1.71
Kakdwip	2.69	4.61	0.58	1.36
Canning	2.69	5.37	0.50	1.73
Kalimpong	2.69	1.54	1.74	-1.38
Islampur	2.30	2.30	1.00	0

with several observations made earlier^{29,30}. Such rapid rates of desorption for the Kalimpong and Islampur soils could possibly be related to the presence of low clay content, as explained earlier, and dominance of weathered micaceous and interstratified minerals in these soils, thus following corresponding low k_a values. However, among the soils, the faster desorption rate coefficients for the soils of Kakdwip and Canning were, possibly, due to dominance of weathered illitic type of minerals characterized by sufficiently fast release of K from wedge zones of 2 : 1 type of minerals. Another contributory factor could be its high salinity which was aided by a high concentration of desorbing electrolyte, namely 0.01 M CaCl₂ (as against much lower concentration of ≈ 0.001 M KCl containing only monovalent cations), in bringing about a high degree of flocculation of the corresponding clays. Sparks and Jardine²⁶ attributed rapid kinetics of K exchange to external planner sites (as in kaolinite), and slower desorption kinetics to inter-lattice exchange sites. The slower desorption kinetics in the soils of Gayeshpur and Memari can partly be attributed to the interlayer sites of the 2 : 1 clay minerals that undergo partial collapse upon K adsorption. These results are also in satisfactory agreement with earlier observations^{2,22}. The Gayeshpur, Memari and Goaltore soils exhibited slower desorption than its adsorption, suggesting that K reactions were non-singular and the hysteresis effect could be operative. Similar observations were reported by Ardakani and McLaren³¹ and Sparks *et al.*⁶. The k_d values were greater than k_a values for some soils, indicating that K desorption was more rapid than K adsorption (Table 7). These data indicate that Ca²⁺ ions were adsorbed more quickly on the readily accessible exchange sites of the soil relative to K⁺ ions.

The values for the standard free energy change for K adsorption (ΔG°) are recorded in Table 7. These values were computed from the relation, $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_{\text{eq}}$ (where, R = universal gas constant, the value being taken as 8.31 J mol⁻¹ deg⁻¹ and T = temperature in absolute scale). In the present study, the overall selectivity of K⁺ against Ca²⁺ was best expressed by these ΔG° values during desorption³². The low ΔG° values implied that a small amount of the energy is left for the system to do the useful work. Thus K⁺ ions would have a limited molecular motion when in contact with these sites. Such a restriction suggests formation of strong bonds between K⁺ ions and some exchange sites of the soils. The soils from Gayeshpur and Memari exhibited high negative ΔG° values compared to those of the Goaltore and Kalimpong soils, indicating strong K preference of these soils over say Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺. Similar observation was made by Goulding and Talibudden³³. Goulding³² found strong K retention in soils that contained substantial quantities of 2 : 1 clay minerals (as in the soils of Gayeshpur and Memari). The Kakdwip and Canning soils exhibited positive ΔG° values. The positive values implied that the driving force for the uptake of K⁺ ion onto exchange complex, initially richer in Ca²⁺ ions, was not favoured thermodynamically in these soils. This might have arisen due to the presence of high amount of soluble salts, especially the Na-salts, the mass action of which resulted in a weak K preference of these soils over Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺.

Potassium adsorption and desorption constants ('a' and 'b') :

The constants 'a' and 'b' of each model represent the intercept and the slope of the linear curves resulting from plotting the adsorbed/desorbed K⁺ vs time (Table 8). The constant 'b' mirrors the fixation and or release rate

Table 8. Adsorption and desorption kinetic parameters of potassium in soils as per different kinetic equations

Kinetic parameters Location of soils	First-order constants		Elovich constants		Parabolic-diffusion constants		Power-function constants		Zero-order constants	
	$\log K_0$	$(k_a \text{ or } k_d) \times 10^{-5} \text{ (min}^{-1}\text{)}$	b	a	a	b	a	b	a	b
Gayeshpur : Adsorption	1.362	3.45	0.7051	3.90×10^7	0.8482	0.0185	0.0405	0.0485	3.133	0.043
Desorption	1.226	0.77	0.6065	1.16×10^2	0.6169	0.0465	0.1249	0.1307	3.646	0.050
Memari : Adsorption	1.276	4.22	0.7205	1.07×10^9	0.8691	0.0156	0.0349	0.0420	3.066	0.040
Desorption	1.416	1.15	0.5057	0.36×10	0.3295	0.0803	0.3244	0.2644	4.357	0.058
Jhargram : Adsorption	1.413	1.92	0.9608	1.55×10^9	0.8745	0.0150	0.0451	0.0409	2.224	0.029
Desorption	1.059	1.92	0.7065	1.45×10^3	0.7130	0.0344	0.0958	0.0977	3.058	0.040
Goaltore : Adsorption	1.293	3.07	0.8120	8.90×10^9	0.8818	0.0141	0.0356	0.0386	2.620	0.034
Desorption	1.280	1.54	0.5327	0.99×10^2	0.6117	0.0461	0.1178	0.1395	4.005	0.052
Kakdwip : Adsorption	1.371	2.69	0.8191	4.49×10^8	0.8656	0.0161	0.0411	0.0433	2.674	0.035
Desorption	1.260	4.61	0.3676	0.81×10	0.3936	0.0729	0.1849	0.2306	5.941	0.079
Canning : Adsorption	1.434	2.69	0.7458	4.59×10^6	0.8329	0.0201	0.0487	0.0542	2.928	0.039
Desorption	1.133	5.37	0.3872	1.30×10	0.4478	0.0666	0.1589	0.2048	5.617	0.075
Kalimpong : Adsorption	1.523	2.69	0.5750	3.39×10^3	0.7286	0.0326	0.0719	0.0918	3.755	0.050
Desorption	1.087	1.54	0.4785	0.28×10	0.2603	0.0880	0.4155	0.3105	4.521	0.059
Islampur : Adsorption	1.592	2.30	0.5725	1.22×10^2	0.6784	0.0502	0.1185	0.1319	2.533	0.051
Desorption	0.799	2.30	0.4768	0.25×10	0.2691	0.0874	0.3941	0.3018	4.532	0.060

of exchangeable and or nonexchangeable K. The 'b' values are known to correlate well with soil K released from the nonexchangeable phase³⁴.

A direct relationship between the first-order K adsorption rate constant (k_a) and the intercept (a) of the parabolic-diffusion equation seemed to be apparent for the present soils (Table 8). Such intercept, measuring the initial K adsorption (at zero time) in a given soil, would be expected to be governed by soil properties, especially the clay content, its make-up as well the weathering history of illitic mineral phase. However, for desorption kinetics, no such trend seemed to be apparent.

The Elovich equation, as stated earlier, did not fit quite as well the experimental kinetic data. From the simplified linear form of the equation it may be noted that a fall in 'b' or a rise in 'a' leads to the increase of adsorption/desorption rates in a given soil. In the present study, soils having high k_a values, in general, showed low 'b' values for K adsorption.

There was a fair degree of inverse relationship between the k_a and the 'a' value (intercept) of the power function equation, where such 'a' values were all less than unity so that $-\ln a$ would be a positive quantity that would fall with a rise in numerical magnitude of 'a' value (Table 8). Such a positive contribution from the intercept ($-\ln a$) of the power function equation to the amount (In

K_t) of the K adsorbed/desorbed in time t would be expected to facilitate the positive relationship between k_a and $\ln K_t$.

The zero-order equation was not generally much useful in explaining the K adsorption and desorption kinetics in the given soils, except in one case, as compared to the other equations discussed^{9,35}. However, it appears that a fair degree of direct relationship exists between the constant 'a' of the zero-order equation and the k_a .

The linear plots for K adsorption and desorption according to parabolic diffusion law (the corresponding R^2 values ranging from 0.938 to 0.998) presented in Fig. 2 suggest that both adsorption and desorption in these soils tended to conform to a diffusion-controlled mechanism^{15,20}. Further, the straight line relationships obtained (in Figs. 1 to 2) suggest that the intraparticle diffusion could be the rate-limiting process²⁶. This emphasizes the importance of the diffusion-controlled exchange mechanism in the given K adsorption/desorption processes.

Experimental

Eight surface soil samples (0–0.15 m) of varying properties were collected from different locations spread over the State of West Bengal. The important physicochemical properties of the soils were probed by having recourse to standard methodologies¹⁸. In particular, the clay minera-

logical make-up of the soils was obtained by X-ray diffraction of the Mg and K saturated clays¹⁹. The clay fractions are also presented in Table 2.

The bulk of kinetic studies with soil have employed batch technique²⁰, which involves placing an exchanger and the adsorbate in a reaction vessel such as a centrifuge tube. In the present study 3 g of each soil and 30 mL of 50 ppm KCl solution were taken in each of several centrifuge tubes, followed by shaking different tubes in a thermostated shaking water bath for different periods such as 5 min, 10 min, 30 min, 50 min, 60 min and 2 h at a temperature of 300 K. A blank tube with soil and distilled water in the same proportions was maintained for each time period. The soil suspension was centrifuged at the expiry of the appropriate time period, and the supernatant was filtered through Whatman No. 42 filter paper. The filtrate was analysed for K flame photometrically. Nonexchangeable K release with time was fitted employing five mathematical models, viz. first-order, Elovich, parabolic-diffusion, power-function and zero-order equations to describe the kinetics of potassium adsorption and desorption in the experimental soils.

For desorption or release studies, the residual soil from the adsorption run was re-suspended in 30 mL of 0.01 M CaCl₂ solution, and shaken for the same time as that during the corresponding adsorption run. The contents of the tubes were then centrifuged and filtered. A blank was also run for each time period. The filtrate was analysed for K flame photometrically.

First-order equation :

A first-order equation for adsorption is expressed as²¹,

$$d(K_0 - K)/dt = k_a \times K$$

where, K = concentration of K⁺ in solution at time t , K_0 = initial concentration of the ion added at zero time and k_a = adsorption rate coefficient.

The integrated form of the equation is

$$\ln K = \ln K_0 - k_a \times t$$

In terms of common logarithms, one obtains,

$$\log K = \log K_0 - (k_a \times t)/2.303$$

The plot of $\log K$ vs t yields a straight line of slope $-k_a$ and an intercept of $\log K_0$, if the data conform to the first order kinetics.

For desorption run, the equation is expressed as²¹,

$$dK_1/dt = k_d (K_0 - K_1)$$

where, K_1 = amount of K⁺ released at time t , K_0 = total

amount of ion that could be released and k_d = desorption rate coefficient.

The desorption or release studies (k_d) of the first-order desorption process was measured from the slope of the linear plot of $\log (K_0 - K_1)$ vs t . Here, K_0 is the total amount of K⁺ ion that could be released and K_1 is the amount released at time t .

For a completely reversible reaction, the thermodynamic equilibrium constant (K_{eq}) for K adsorption was obtained from the relation²²,

$$K_{eq} = k_a/k_d$$

The Gibbs standard free energy change (ΔG°) for the given exchange process was obtained from the following equation,

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_{eq}$$

where, R = universal gas constant and T = absolute temperature.

Elovich equation :

The Elovich equation applied to K release is expressed as

$$dy/dt = ae^{-by}$$

where, y = amount of K adsorbed or released at time t (K_t), a , b = constants.

The constant a represents the initial rate since $dy/dt \rightarrow a$ as $y \rightarrow 0$. Assuming $y = 0$ at $t = 0$, the integrated form of equation is

$$K_t = (1/b) \ln (1 + abt) \quad [\text{putting } y = K_t]$$

If, $abt \gg 1$, then the above equation can be simplified to

$$K_t = (1/b) \ln (abt) + (1/b) \ln t$$

Thus a plot of K_t vs $\ln t$ should be linear with slope $1/b$ and intercept $(1/b) \ln (ab)$.

Parabolic diffusion equation :

The parabolic equation for K exchange may be represented as²³,

$$K_t/K_0 = (4\pi^{1/2}) (Dt/a_1^2)^{1/2} - (Dt/a_1^2)$$

where, K_t = quantity of K on the exchange sites of the soil at time t , K_0 = quantity of K on the exchange sites of the soil at equilibrium, a_1 = radius parameter (cylindrical radius of the area through which K diffuses) and D = diffusion coefficient.

In soils with numerous types of clays of varying particle sizes, a realistic value of a_1 is not usually measurable, thus D can not be measured either²⁴. Thus the equation must be arbitrarily simplified to :

$$K_t/K_0 = D_a t^{1/2}$$

where, D_a = apparent diffusion rate coefficient.

Thus a plot of (K_t/K_0) vs $t^{1/2}$ should provide a linear relationship if the reaction conforms to diffusion-controlled process or Fickian diffusion.

Power-function equation :

The integrated form of power-function equation is given by

$$y = at^b$$

The linear transformation is

$$\ln K_t = b \ln t - \ln a \text{ [putting } y = K_t]$$

where, K_t = quantity of K adsorbed or desorbed at time t , a, b = constants.

Zero-order equation :

$$K_0 - K_t = a - bt$$

where, K_t = maximum amount of K adsorbed or desorbed, K_t = amount of K adsorbed or desorbed in time t and a, b = constants.

The above equations were tested by the least square regression analysis for K adsorption and desorption in the soils to ascertain as to which equation best described the kinetic data. The coefficient of determination (R^2) and the standard error of estimate (S.E.) as defined by Martin and Sparks¹⁴ were calculated for each equation using the relationship,

$$\text{S.E.} = [\sum(y_0 - y_e)^2 / (n - 2)]^{1/2}$$

where, y_0 and y_e are the measured and calculated concentration of K adsorbed and desorbed at time t and n is the number of measurements⁷.

The adsorption rate coefficient (k_a) was calculated from graphical plot of $\log K$ vs t which yielded a straight line of slope $-k_a$ according to the first-order kinetics of K adsorption by the given soils²¹. Here K denotes the concentration of K^+ in the filtrate at time t .

The desorption rate coefficient (k_d) of the first-order desorption process was measured from the slope of the linear plots of $\log (K_0 - K_t)$ vs t . Here, K_0 is the total amount of K^+ ion that could be released and K_t is the amount released at time t ²¹.

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